

Antiplasticisation of Tri-Aryl Ether Epoxies

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Air Travel and Pollution

Air Travel = most climate damaging form of transportation

Weight of plane = more fuel consumption = add cost to flying and environmental impact

Emission of green house gases = climate change

4.6B people flying in 2019

SOLUTION: Light Weight High Strength Plastic-Fiber Composite = Fuel Saving

Carbon Fiber-Epoxy Composites

6X lighter than steel

rigid **strong**

tough

environment resistant

Composite → **Carbon fiber** → **Very rigid and strong**

Polymer matrix → **So much weaker!** → **Property mismatch**

Objectives

- ❖ Improve the quality of the epoxy matrix by varying the backbone chemistry of the monomer
 - incorporate backbone with difference aromatic substitution patterns (meta and para)
- ❖ Toughen the matrix without reduction in glass transition temperature (T_g)
 - sustain modulus, strength and strain-to-failure

Design of Molecular Backbone of Epoxies

Methodology

Synthesis of epoxy building blocks

Analysis of molecular structure

1:0.9 epoxy-hardener formulation

Melting, mixing and degassing

Casting in silicone moulds

Epoxy-Amine curing (180°C)

Photographs of cured resin bars and cylinders

Results and Discussion

Conclusion

- Two resins were synthesised and cured with different amines
- Their aryl backbones have unique meta and para substitution pattern: improved displacement-to-failure with sustained or increased modulus and strength (antiplasticisation)
- The mechanical properties of resins with more meta substitution in the network were superior over their all-para counterparts
- T_g of all tetra-functional epoxies were high
- Future work, change central ring to:
 - Benzophenone
 - Naphthalene
 - Biphenyl

Reference

[1] R. Ramsdale-Capper and J. P. Foreman. *Polym.*, vol. 146, pp. 321–330, 2018.
[2] Vogel, Wouter et al. 2014. *High Perf. Polymers* 26(4): 420–35.